

MINOAS NEWSLETTERS

MINOAS key achievements of September | Papers | White papers | Keynotes | Poster | Market size analysis | Dissemination | Milestones |

Milestones

The following seven (7) milestones of MINOAS has been completed:

- Availability of MINOAS's public profiles (Month 02)
- Availability of Deliverable D1.1 (Month 03)
- Availability of the initial version of the optics-signal interface (Month 03)
- Availability of vision video at YouTube (Month 04)
- Availability of D1.2 (Month 05)
- Availability of requirements and specifications (Month 05)
- Availability of MINOAS system architecture (Month 07)

Papers

The MINOAS project has already published four (4) journal papers in high-impactful venues:

- 1 in IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications
- 1 in IEEE Wireless Communication Letters

Holographic RIS Empowered THz Communications with Hardware Imperfections under Adverse Weather Conditions

Alexandros-Apostolos A. Boulogeorgos, Senior Member, IEEE, Stylianos E. Trevlakis, Member, IEEE, and Theodoros A. Tziftsis, Senior Member, IEEE

Abstract—This paper focuses on providing a theoretical framework for the evaluation of the performance of holographic reconfigurable intelligent surface (HRIS) empowered terahertz (THz) wireless systems under fog conditions. In more detail, we present a comprehensive methodology for evaluating the geometric losses of the end-to-end channel. Moreover, the stochastic nature of the end-to-end channel is characterized by novel closed-form probability density and cumulative distribution functions. Building upon them, the outage probability and the throughput of the system are extracted in closed form. These formulas account for the impact of transceiver hardware imperfections and are expected to become useful tools for the design of HRIS empowered THz wireless systems due to its remarkable engineering insights.

Index Terms—Fog, hardware imperfections, holographic reconfigurable intelligent surface (HRIS), outage probability, stochastic characterization, throughput.

put on modeling the deterministic path loss of THz wireless links [7]–[10]. In more detail, in [7], the authors employed the radiation theory in order to extract the channel characteristics of nano-scale THz wireless links. In [8], an electromagnetic analysis was conducted for the propagation characterization of in-body THz links, while in [9], the authors presented a path loss model for in-body nano-scale THz wireless systems. A simplified path loss model for THz systems operating in the 275 – 400 GHz region was presented in [10].

Another important drawback of THz wireless systems is the signal fluctuation due to atmospheric conditions. The source of this phenomenon lies in the variation of the reflection index, as a result of inhomogeneities in atmospheric pressure as well as temperature and water molecular density across the propagation path [11]. Inspired by this, the authors of [12]

Journal Paper “Holographic RIS Empowered THz Communications with Hardware Imperfections under Adverse Weather Conditions”

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Journal: IEEE Transactions on Communications (Impact Factor: 7.2)

- 1 in IEEE Transactions on Communications
- 1 in IEEE Journal of Internet of Things

Additionally, the MINOAS project has under review one (1) more journal paper, which

Finally, we have published one (1) conference paper in the following prestigious international conference:

- 1 in IEEE GLOBECOM.

Keynotes

The MINOAS project has completed the following five (5) keynote presentations:

- 1 in International conference on communication, devices and networking
- 1 in International Conference on Advanced Engineering, Technology and Applications
- 1 in WINC Workshop and Nanonetworking Day 2024
- 1 in IEEE/CIC International Conference on Communications in China
- 1 in GLOBAL 5G Evolution

White papers

MINOAS has started the preparation of its first white paper on optical communications use cases requirements and specifications.

Optimal Operation of Active RIS-Aided Wireless Powered Communications in IoT Networks

Waqas Khalid, Alexandros-Apostolos A. Boulogeorgos, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Trinh Van Chien, *Member, IEEE*, Junse Lee, *Member, IEEE*, Howon Lee, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Heejung Yu, *Senior Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Wireless-powered communications (WPCs) are increasingly crucial for extending the lifespan of low-power Internet of Things (IoT) devices. Furthermore, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) can create favorable electromagnetic environments by providing alternative signal paths to counteract blockages. The strategic integration of WPC and RIS technologies can significantly enhance energy transfer and data transmission efficiency. However, passive RISs suffer from double-fading attenuation over RIS-aided cascaded links. In this article, we propose the application of an active RIS within WPC-enabled IoT networks. The enhanced flexibility of the active RIS in terms of energy transfer and information transmission is investigated using adjustable parameters. We derive novel closed-form expressions for the ergodic rate and outage probability by incorporating key parameters, including signal amplification, active noise, power consumption, and phase quantization errors. Additionally, we explore the optimization of WPC scenarios, focusing on the time-switching factor and power consumption of

diverse devices via wireless channels and Internet gateways, with a focus on self-sustainability to minimize maintenance costs [1]–[4]. Self-powered wireless devices can harvest energy from external sources, such as sun, wind, and vibrations. However, their performance is often dependent on natural factors, such as weather conditions. Recently, radio frequency (RF)-based power transfer has gained considerable attention due to its adaptability, flexibility, wide coverage, and low-complexity implementation [5]. Wireless-powered communication (WPC) represents a green networking paradigm that integrates wireless information transmission and power transfer [6]. In WPC systems, devices achieve self-sustainability by efficiently harvesting energy from RF signals, thereby reducing the need for frequent battery replacement. This approach enhances throughput, extends battery life, and lowers operational

Journal Paper “Optimal Operation of Active RIS-Aided Wireless Powered Communications in IoT Networks”

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Journal: IEEE Internet of Things Journal (Impact Factor: 8.2)

Your opinion matters!

- Which do you believe is the key limited factor in optical wireless links?
 - 20% of the participants answered blockage
 - 67% of the participants voted misalignment & disorientation
 - 7% of the participants answered hardware imperfections, and
 - 7% of the participants voted for power limitations

- Which do you think is the order of data rate that a 1 km FSO link can achieve?
 - Mbps
 - Gbps
 - Tbps
 - Pbps

Fluid Antenna Wireless Systems for Enhanced Spectrum Sensing

Leila Tlebaldiyeva*, Sultangali Arzykulov*, Alexandros-Apostolos A. Boulogeorgos[†], Theodoros A. Tsiftsis[‡], and Galymzhan Nauryzbayev*

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Abstract—An exponentially growing number of internet-of-things (IoT) devices is expected to bring wireless networks to their limits due to the resulting bandwidth scarcity problem. To counterbalance bandwidth bottlenecks, novel design configurations for radio-frequency components that bring flexibility and reconfigurability to modern IoT networks wireless networks are required. Moreover, next-generation networks are expected to support incredibly high data rates, massive connectivity, latency, energy, and cost-critical applications. In this direction, operators opened the door to the millimeter wave (mmWave) band. However, mmWave communications come with limitations. Two of the most important limiting factors are the high path loss and the high penetration loss due to blockage. Possible approaches to constrain the impact of these factors while exploiting the underutilized spectrum lie in spectrum sensing/sharing and spatial diversity. Spectrum sensing allows secondary IoT users to detect spectrum holes and utilize the licensed bandwidth without causing interference to primary users. In this work, we introduce the implementation of an energy detector for spectrum sensing by using the fluid antenna system (FAS), which increases spatial diversity and improves the detection probability. Due to the dense employment of multiple antenna ports over a half-wavelength order antenna length, FAS can fit up to hundreds of antenna ports. This work presents a newly derived analytical expression for the average detection probability given FAS receiver over correlated Nakagami- m fading channels. Numerical results demonstrate that FAS considerably enhances the energy detector's performance.

Index Terms—Energy detector, Fluid antenna system (FAS)

services, ultimately leading to optimized network resource allocation and high performance.

According to [3], [4], licensed spectrum is primarily underutilized, and spectrum sensing/sharing techniques of CR are expected to improve SE. Energy detectors are the most common tools for identifying spectrum holes. Energy detectors have been widely investigated in the context of traditional receivers [3], [5]. The critical challenge that is faced in energy detection-assisted spectrum sensing is that to support a high detection probability, the false alarm probability that is achieved is also relatively high.

Recently, fluid antenna systems (FASs) have been presented as an alternative to conventional solid antennas with advanced reconfiguration and adaptation capabilities. FASs offer high diversity gains [6]. Moreover, reconfigurability is a significant advantage of FAS, enabling it to dynamically change its shape, frequency, and radiation pattern, allowing IoT devices to adapt and optimize to ever-changing environments. Another vital advantage is the antenna's mechanical flexibility. Unlike rigid solid antennas, fluid antennas can be integrated into flexible and conformal surfaces, enabling them to be used in applications such as wearable electronics, conformal aircraft antennas, and shape-shifting communication systems [7]. The authors of [8] designed a multi-beam conformal antenna built

Conference Paper “Fluid Antenna Wireless Systems for Enhanced Spectrum Sensing”

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Communication & dissemination achievements

Till the seventh month of the project MINOAS, we achieved the following in terms of communication & dissemination:

- MINOAS Website visitors > 1000
- YouTube channel viewers > 1000
- YouTube channel videos = 15
- LinkedIn group members > 800
- Accepted journal papers = 4
- Accepted conference papers = 1
- Preprints = 1
- White papers = 1
- Submitted journal papers = 2
- Submitted conference papers = 2
- Patents filled = 3
- Keynote presentations = 4
- No. Webinars organised = 1

implementation of an energy detector for spectrum sensing by using the fluid antenna system (FAS), which increases spatial diversity and improves the detection probability. Due to the dense employment of multiple antenna ports over a half-wavelength order antenna length, FAS can fit up to hundreds of antenna ports. This work presents a newly derived analytical expression for the average detection probability given FAS receiver over correlated Nakagami-m fading channels. Numerical results demonstrate that FAS considerably enhances the energy detector's performance.

Conference: IEEE GLOBECOM 2024

MINOAS Poster

Χρηματοδότηση της Βασικής Έρευνας

MINOAS
Machine learning aided optical wireless networks

Δικαιούχοι:

Φορέας Υλοποίησης:
 ΕΛΙΑΔΕΚ
Ελληνικό Κέντρο Έρευνας Καινοτομίας

Προϋπολογισμός έργου:
189.250,00 €

Το έργο υλοποιείται στο πλαίσιο της Δράσης «Ενίσχυση Βασικής και Εφαρμοσμένης Έρευνας» του Ταμείου Ανάκαμψης και Ανθεκτικότητας

ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ
ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΑΝΑΠΤΥΞΗΣ

Ελλάδα 2.0
ΕΘΝΙΚΟ ΣΧΕΔΙΟ ΑΝΑΚΑΜΨΗΣ ΚΑΙ ΑΝΘΕΚΤΙΚΟΤΗΤΑΣ

Με τη χρηματοδότηση της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης
NextGenerationEU

Get in touch with us

- Website: <https://minoas-project.gr/>
- YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@minoas-project>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-minoas/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61552919412515>
- Coordinator information: Alexandros-Apostolos A. Boulogeorgos (aboulogeorgos@uowm.gr)

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MINOAS flyer

MINOAS pillars

- Pillar I: Beyond Shannon Optical wireless communications for high-data rate,
- Pillar II: AI-based optical wireless network orchestration to maximize the system's energy efficiency,
- Pillar III: "Almost-zero latency" and high-computational capabilities at the

Optical wireless communications - Market size analysis

MINOAS-Machine Learning Aided Optical Wireless Network

The project MINOAS has lunched in November 2023 with the vision of bringing the fiber quality of experience (QoE) and reliability to the wireless world. You can find more information about the project and the results in the following link: <https://minoas-project.gr>.

Key Drivers

1. Increasing demand for high-data rate connectivity
2. Advancements in telecommunication technology
3. Establishing global internet penetration
4. Growing telecommunication traffic worldwide
5. Need for "greener" telecommunications
6. Advancements in nanotechnology

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MINOAS-project: Optical wireless communications-Market size analysis

Get in touch with us

- Website: <https://minoas-project.gr/>
- YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@minoas-project>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-minoas/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61552919412515>
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Did you know that...

Did you know that....

1 simple email is responsible for 4 grams of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere.

1-hour video emits approximately 55 grams of CO₂ on average

The internet's annual energy consumption is around 200-250 TWh globally.

Stay tuned to find out the MINOAS solutions towards a more sustainable future....

Greece 2.0
NATIONAL RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE PLAN

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